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Attitude towards Private Labels

An Empirical Study of Sensory Evaluation of Packaged Food by Young Indian Consumers

Sushil Kr. Dixit *

ABSTRACT

Present study aims to extend the understanding of consumers' perception of private label food products among Indian youths. The paper is in three parts. In the first part the purchase behavior of Indian youth for private label products in general and groceries, food, apparels and toiletries as categories is examined. Impact of gender, disposable family income and lifestyle is examined specifically. In the second part effort has been made to find some of the reasons for purchase of private labels. In the third part impact of extrinsic cues such as information about brand, manufacturer etc was examined on hedonic judgment of consumers with the help of consumer sensory test of potato chips in two experimental conditions. The difference between private label and producer label (National Brands) products was especially examined. Results show that consumers in India perceive private labels as a lower price alternative of comparable quality to manufacturers' brands. Gender, disposable family income and life style proved to have significant effect on propensity to buy private label products. Study confirms that the extrinsic cues such as brand etc significantly affect consumer sensory judgment. Attitude towards Private Labels

INTRODUCTION

Currently, Indian market is witnessing a retail boom with organized retailers offering a whole assortment of goods and services under one roof with good shopping environment. After agriculture, retail is the second largest employer in India. In India retailing sector is fragmented and predominantly consists of small, independently and owner-managed shops. There is a boom in the retail trade in India owing to a gradual increase in the disposable income of the middle-class household. More and more national and international players are entering in the market with new attractive retail formats like malls, supermarkets, departmental stores etc. India Retail Report (2007) reviewed that food and grocery comprises 62 per cent of the (\$ 270 billion or Rs. 1200000 crore) Indian retail market. Recent studies show that in supermarket industry, the balance of power in the grocery channel has shifted in favor of retailers. To support this phenomenon we can give the

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example of the growing use of slotting allowances to obtain shelf space, the surge in trade promotions, and the proliferation of private brands, which account for about 20% of U.S. and 20-30% of European supermarket sales (Dunne and Narasimhan, 1999; Steenkamp and Dekimpe, 1997).

The market share of private brands has increased in several product categories, accounting for almost 15% of overall sales in 1996 (Hoch 1996). The retailers are using store brands as an important competitive tool (Putsis and Dhar 1998). In India the contribution of organized retail sector is only 4% of the total retail market. So the market of store brands is just at the introduction stage. The big players like Big Bazaar, Reliance Super, Spencers, Chroma, Vishal Mega Mart, Westside etc have come up with store brands in different product categories.

In private brands the retailers are performing the dual role of retailer and manufacturer. So the traditional role of both the parties is changing. Retailers are transforming themselves from pure customers to the manufacturers of national brands to direct competitors to the manufactures (Dhar and Hoch, 1997).

Most of organized retail players carry processed packaged food as one of the category. The organized retailers have successfully adopted the strategy of introducing private label and introduced packaged food products as a category giving direct competition to national brands. In the beginning these retailers introduced private label products as a mechanism to increase profitability as these provide higher margins. But in later phases these packaged food items also serve other motives like store image building, increasing customer loyalty etc. of the retailers.

A food product is defined as an aggregation of attributes at different levels. According to Grunert et al. (2000) these are: search attributes (e.g. price, colour), experience attributes (e.g. taste and flavour) and credence attributes (e.g. health and safety). These attributes are considered as evaluative criteria in consumer's purchase decisions and are transposed to consumer perception through a process of interaction of product characteristics and personal socio-demographic, economic, psychographic, behavioural and cognitive determinants (Mowen, 1993). Food selection and consumption is therefore a complex phenomenon influenced by a multitude of factors.

Individual socio-demographic and economic characteristics are commonly included when consumers are making a purchasing decision and they have to form quality expectations based on quality cues (Tuorila et al., 1998). Consumers form their quality expectation for most of the food categories on extrinsic cues such as price, brand name,

brand familiarity, advertisements, etc. as intrinsic cues such as taste, flavor etc can not be evaluated in packaged food products. The effects of extrinsic cues on consumer behavior and its effect on consumer expectations have been widely studied (for a review see Deliza and MacFie, 1996). Price has been considered as a very important cue and received a great part of the research attention. However, in the literature (Jacoby et al., 1971) the theory that price is an objective cue, contrary to other factors being defined as subjective was established. In addition, for the regularity of brand's usage the most frequently read information about the foodstuff selected is important (Chernatony, 1991). Keller (2002) identified the following key functions of the brand for consumers: identification of origin; definition of responsibility of producer; risk reduction; search cost reduction and a virtual contract with producer (promise, guarantee). While Deliza and MacFie (1996) put the main focus of brand on informational cue. Consumers combine actual information from shopping environment with past experiences and use them to make purchase decision, but they strive for a "cognitive efficiency" and try to use minimum of information. As a result, they use brand as a simplifier of a decision making process and hence the foundation of brand power.

There is clear evidence from research work that non-sensory attributes of food (extrinsic cues) affect the sensory acceptability of a food product (Di Monaco et al., 2003). However, external attributes mainly affect purchase decision, while sensory attributes confirm liking of a product and therefore determine repeat purchase and loyalty. Rather large research attention has been devoted to the effect of brand on overall liking and sensory evaluation of food (Deliza and MacFie, 1996).

It has been pointed out that the effect of a brand in the food choice is also largely dependant on individual characteristics of consumers and it is possible to distinguish them regarding to their sensitivity to brand. The effect of brand on consumer is well represented in scientific literature, however there are much less studies regarding the private labels. DelVecchio (2001) prepared a research focusing on the role of product category characteristics on private label perception and acceptability. He found that the consumer perception and penetration success of private label is driven by the segment complexity, quality variance, price and inter-purchase time. The private label shopper has been identified as price sensitive but not promotion sensitive (Baltas, 1997). In purchase decisions generally high importance is given to the familiarity with the product.

The objective of the present study is to extend understanding about private label purchase behavior. The paper examines impact of socio demographic factors on purchase of private labels. Reasons for the purchase of private labels by Indian youth have also been examined. The main objective is to examine to which extent an extrinsic factor

(information on brand) affects hedonic sensory judgment and whether there is a difference in respect to the type of brand. A direct comparison has been made between national brands and private labels.

The research focuses on young Indian packaged food consumers in NCR in India. The reason for selecting young Indian consumers is that they form one of the largest segment visiting large super markets in India. With increasing employment opportunities for the younger generation in post liberalization era in Indian cities the income level of this segment has significantly increased. This increased income with higher proportion of disposable income is creating demand in urban India for a number of product categories such as packaged processed food, consumer durables, electronic gadgets, housing etc. Thus, this segment represents one of the very attractive segments from the perspective of the marketer.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in two consecutive stages. First, two focus groups were formed with 6 participants in each, discussing food purchasing behavior with special attention to private label food products. These focus groups were composed of eight females and four male young consumers. At the final stage of each focus group a preliminary consumer sensory evaluation test was performed. The latter was intended to determine the consumer sensory evaluation of food products. Potato chips were selected to serve as a research object since they offer a rather limited possibility for product differentiation. Furthermore, potato chips are widely available and used in India and these were among the first sold food product under private label.

Wording of consumers relating to the private labels was carefully studied from the focus groups discussions and used while preparing the questionnaire as suggested by Malholtra (2007).

The second part of the research was a consumer study in two sessions with an attitude questionnaire containing socio demography, purchase behavior and sensory evaluation test involving 70 participants.

The current study was conducted using a non probability convenience sampling due to limited finance and time. This type of sample allows the researcher to basically choose who, where and when to research and gather data. One of the disadvantages of this method is that the result may be non representative of the entire population. However this method is quite common in business and management research as this can ensure a

high response rate whereas probability sampling involves a lot of difficulty and costs.

Table 1
Basic Demographic Detail of the Sample

<i>Age group</i>	<i>Gender</i>		<i>Total %</i>
	<i>Male %</i>	<i>Female %</i>	
Less than 20	8.6	8.6	17.1
20-25	17.1	32.9	50.0
25-30	22.9	10.0	32.9
Total	48.6	51.4	100.0
Minimum	Maximum	Average	Std. Deviation
19	28	23	3.00

Survey was conducted at Apeejay Institute of Technology, Greater Noida, India among its students. First, the participants were asked to fill the first part of the questionnaire. After that they were asked to express their opinion about the samples of potato chips served to them on a ten-point hedonic scale. Five brands of potato chips Two national label, two private labels and one local label widely available in Indian market were included. In the first session samples were served in neutral plastic containers labeled with a random alphabetical code - so called "blind tasting". After some time in the second session participants were served from the original packaging of potato chips and hence they were informed about the brand ("informed tasting"). After both the tasting sessions consumers completed the second and third part of the questionnaire by indicating their liking of a particular sample on a ten point hedonic scale.

For the purposes of this experiment it was sufficient to ask consumers for simple judgment on general acceptability (level of likeness) of the product without indicating specific sensory characteristic. It is believed that consumers make hedonic judgment considering the product as a whole and are generally not able to concentrate on singular sensory characteristics.

Table 2
Experimental Design

<i>Experimental conditions</i>	<i>No. of subjects</i>	<i>Identification of samples</i>
Blind	70	Alphabetical Code
Informed	70	Brand Name

Results from the consumer questionnaire were processed using general descriptive statistical methods. In order to evaluate the effect of the information about brand etc on the hedonic judgment the difference between informed and blind ratings for different sample of potato chips was calculated (I-B). Paired samples t-test was used to evaluate the statistical significance of the rating difference.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results from the consumer questionnaire mainly confirm the evident trend of increasing youth interest in private label products in the region. As much as 37.1 percent of the respondents reported as frequent buyer of private label products in general. 38.6 percent reported as occasional buyer of private label products. Only 24.3% respondents reported as rare buyer of private label products. Thus almost 75.7 percent respondents can be categorized as active potential to be effectively targeted by the private label marketers.

Table 3
Store Brand Purchase

Purchase Behavior	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Rarely	17	24.3	24.3
Occasionally	27	38.6	62.9
Frequently	26	37.1	100.0
Total	70	100.0	

Table below shows category wise purchase frequency of private labels. It also shows mean responses for different categories of private labels purchase frequency with the corresponding standard deviations. From the table it is evident that apparels is the most appealing private label category for youth in the region with 78.6 percent respondent reporting as frequent and occasional buyer. The mean frequency is also highest for apparels

as a category. Second important category is of packaged food items with 78.6 percent respondent reporting as frequent and occasional buyer, because for this category respondents reporting as frequent buyer are lesser then in case of apparels. The third important category for the youths was of groceries items 67.5 percent reporting as frequent and actual buyers. The toiletries as a category of private labels have lowest appeal for the youth in the region. The mean frequency was also reported as lowest in case of toiletries.

Table 4
Category Wise Private Label Purchase Frequency

Purchase Behavior	Groceries %	Food %	Apparels %	Toiletries %
Rare	28.6	21.4	21.4	47.1
Occasional	42.9	48.6	44.3	30.0
Frequent	28.6	30.0	34.3	22.9
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Mean	2.00	2.09	2.13	1.76
Standard Deviation	.761	1.000	.741	.806

It is therefore possible to conclude that apparels and packaged food are the product categories with high potentials for private label penetration among youths in the region. The reason for this trend may be increasing interest of Indian youths in apparels and packaged food items because of the changing life style and values of the Indian youths. Another reason may be the strategy of "differentiation prevention" which is being successfully followed by many of the private labels. Most of the processed food items under the private labels are similar to the products sold under the manufacturer brands.

It was also attempted to discover whether the propensity to buy private labels is associated with the gender, family income level and life style of the consumers.

It was found that the female prefer to purchase private label more regularly in comparison to male consumers. Probably the reason may be that the females in India are more price conscious then the male consumers and private labels are available at a little lower price in comparison to national brands. 21.4% females reported as frequent buyer of private label products in comparison to 15.7% male consumers.

Table 5
Gender Private Label Purchase Relationship

Gender	Store Brand Purchase Frequency							
	Rarely		Occasionally		Frequently		Total	
	Count	Percent	Count	Percent	Count	Percent	Count	Percent
Male	9	12.9	14	20.0	11	15.7	34	48.6
Female	8	11.	13	18.6	15	21.4	236	51.4
Total	17	24.3	27	38.6	26	37.1	70	100.0

($p = .721$, Pearson Chi-Square = .655)

Self-reported household disposable income has shown statistically significant effect on private label purchase frequency ($p = 0.000$) with evident negative dependency (Gamma -0.663). Respondents in middle income groups are more frequent buyers of private label products in comparison to higher and lower income group.

Table 6
Impact of the Disposable Income on the Frequency of Private Label Purchase

Income Group	Frequency of Private Label Purchase (in percent)			
	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Total
Less than 2 Lac	0.0	0.0	12.9	12.9
2-4 lac	1.4	20.0	10.0	31.4
4-6 lac	10.0	12.9	12.9	35.7
More Than 6 lac	12.9	5.7	1.4	20.0
Total	24.3	38.6	37.1	100.0

($p = 0.000$; $n = 70$; Gamma - 0.663)

We also tried to find relation between lifestyle of the respondents and private label purchase behavior. For the purpose respondents were classified as innovators, strivers and traditionalists. They were asked to identify the appropriate lifestyle which they follow and tick it in the questionnaire. These terms were defined as:

- Innovators : Self-confident risk-takers, seeking new and different things, setting their own targets to achieve.
- Strivers : Attach importance to image and status, as a means of enabling acceptance by their peer group, at the same time holding onto traditional values.
- Traditionalists : Risk averse, guided by traditional behaviors and values, quiet and reserved, hanging back and blending in with the crowd.

Table 6
Impact of Consumer's Life Style on Private Label Purchase Frequency

Life Style	Store Brand Purchase Frequency							
	Rarely		Occasionally		Frequently		Total	
	Count	Percent	Count	Percent	Count	Percent	Count	Percent
Traditionalist	9	12.9	5	7.1	5	7.1	19	27.1
Strivers	5	7.1	14	20.0	8	11.4	27	38.6
Innovators	5	7.1	7	10.0	12	17.1	24	34.3
Total	19	27.1	26	37.1	25	35.7	70	100.0

(p = 0.070; n = 70, Chi Square = 8.660)

Table 6 indicates that Innovators and Strivers life style consumers prefer to purchase private label more then the consumers who follow a traditionalist life style. However the impact was found to be statistically insignificant (p = 0.070; n = 70, Chi Square = 8.660)

To find the reasons for the purchase of private label products some questions were used in the questionnaire and the respondents were asked to indicate their opinion about a given statement on a five point Likert scale where one represented strong disagreement and 5 represented strong agreement with the given statement. The table below presents summary statistics for the questions asked.

Table 7
Statistics Relating To Reasons for Purchase of Private Labels

No.	Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
1	PL is generally Lower Priced then National Brands.	4.26	.811	-1.013	.701
2	Quality of PL is similar to that of national brands.	4.23	.837	-.458	-1.425
3	When I purchase PL I get Good Value for Money.	5.07	1.448	-.983	.210
4	Price as Indicator of Quality	2.34	1.339	1.129	.807
5	I do not purchase PL because these are not conveniently available.	3.06	1.075	.028	-.226
6	Availability of PL at large store lead to forced purchasing of other items.	3.23	1.079	-.545	-.143
7	I prefer to purchase PL from well known retailers.	2.91	1.401	.124	-1.143
8	I prefer to purchase PL from retailers whom I trust.	3.89	.941	-.411	-.740
9	I purchase PL on the recommendation of my friends.	3.77	1.079	-.096	-1.138
10	I purchase private labels when these are endorsed by eminent personalities.	2.36	.745	.806	.567

From the table it is clear that the primary reason for the purchase of private labels is that the consumers get a good value of the money from the purchases. The mean of the responses is highest for this case. The youth also strongly believe that the private labels are generally priced lower then the national brands and the quality of private labels is similar to that of national brands. From the first four statements it is clear that the youth in the region wants a good value for the money and also believes that the price is not an indicator of the quality. Probably the reason for this may be high level of awareness of the youths in the region. The respondents also reported their preference towards non purchase of private labels because of the reason that these are not available conveniently and to visit large retail outlets to purchase private labels also results in forced purchase of the item either which are not required or in larger quantities then what is required. In retailer related features the respondents preferred to purchase private labels from the retailers whom they trust then from the well known retailers. This indicates that the retailers who enjoy high level of trust with the buyers can leverage this trust by launching private labels in associated

categories. As far as marketing communication or advertising is concerned statement 9 and 10 indicates that the consumers give more weight to word of mouth (i.e. positive statement from friends) then endorsement of private label products by celebrities in advertisement campaigns.

The results from the consumer evaluation of potato chips are presented in the Tab. 8 which shows mean liking scores for five samples in two experimental conditions. In case of blind testing highest mean ranking score of 6.21 was given to Sample D which is a leading private label from the well known organized retailer in India. This manufacturer is also known for its aggressive private label promotion and marketing strategies. Another private label which is Sample B reported a mean score of 6.10 and received third rank. Sample C and Sample A which are leading national brands reported second and fourth ranking in the blind testing with mean liking score of 6.17 and 5.93. Lowest mean score of 4.34 was given to Sample D which is locally available low quality product.

The mean liking score for Sample A and Sample C, which are leading national brands rose significantly in informed testing (when the respondents knew the brand) and was reported at 7.09 and 7.49 (in both the cases $p=0.000$). So, this data confirm an assimilation effect due to a positive image of the brand. It is concluded that the extrinsic cues, especially the information about the brand affect hedonic sensory judgment of the consumers.

Table 8
Mean Liking Scores of Hedonic Sensory Evaluation and
Effect of Information about Brand

Sample Code	Mean Liking Score		Standard deviation		Mean Difference	Significance (2-tailed)
	Blind	Informed	Blind	Informed		
A	5.93	7.09	1.220	1.087	-1.157	.000
B	6.10	6.56	1.218	.987	-.457	.000
C	6.17	7.49	.963	.717	-1.314	.000
D	6.21	6.86	1.473	1.447	-.643	.012
E	4.34	4.04	1.202	1.209	.300	.085

The liking score for Sample D which is a leading private label owned by one of the

well known national organized retailer with aggressive private label marketing strategy in Indian market also rose significantly ($p=.012$) in informed testing (when the respondents knew the brand) and was reported at 6.86. In case of Sample B which is also a recently launched private label product by another retailer the mean reported rose significantly from blind testing ($p=.000$). In this case also an assimilation effect of information about brand and origin is concluded.

Very close mean liking score has been given to Sample E which is a locally available generic product in both blind and informed testing. In fact the mean difference was lowest in this case. Information on the brand has no significant ($p=.085$) effect in the case of the E sample. However both average liking scores were lowest. The quality of this product obviously does not correspond to the expectations of Indian consumers. For this sample there was no considerable difference in means in blind and informed testing. Thus, respondents in the study attested as rather reliable sensory evaluations.

CONCLUSION

Thus the study confirms growing preference of private label products by Indian youths. Apparels and packaged food products seems to be preferred categories of private labels. Gender and reported family income shows significant relation with the private label purchase frequency. Reported Life style does not show significant relation with the purchase of private labels.

Study confirms that Indian consumers are price sensitive. Significant reason for purchase of private labels is that with a similar quality these are available at a little lower price than the national brands. Private labels also give good value for their money. It was also found that the youth in the region does not believe that the price is an indicator of quality. Consumers prefer to purchase private labels from the store that they trust then from the large stores. It was also found that in case of private labels positive word of mouth from friends is more effective than celebrity endorsements. However, it was reported that the private labels are not conveniently available and visiting shopping malls to purchase private labels result in forced purchases of unwanted items or quantities. Thus to succeed retailers must find way to conveniently deliver quality private labels at a lower price to consumers. To develop trust, guarantee may be offered by a familiar retail store on a cheaper product and all efforts should be made to have a widespread positive word of mouth about the store and product.

The study confirms that the information about brand can significantly affect consumers' hedonic sensory judgment of food. Consumer sensory judgment is therefore influenced by past experiences, familiarity, advertising etc. and preference is therefore influenced by more than the taste of food itself. When comparing the impact of experimental condition with respect to the type of brand, we observed the effect of assimilation also in the case of private label products which might be explained by responses from the attitudinal questions and actual market conditions in India. It has been noticed that consumers have a set of expectation related to a certain private labels which is furthermore influenced by the perceived image of the retailer. In case where the retailer has a reputation of offering private labels of high quality assimilation revealed has been positive. It might be therefore inferred that consumers when making sensory evaluation are influenced similarly by the private label and producer label e.g. there is no difference regarding the type of label. These findings contribute to complex matter and have important implications for strategic brand management. Consumers do not perceive private labels as a "second class" label also in the case when the segment is non-diversified and only first generation private labels exist. Indian private label shoppers might be identified as a price-cautious but quality-sensitive. This can be inferred from the results of Sample E. This highlights the necessity of permanent low price strategy for private label food and preventing differentiation from the producer brands in respect of perceived quality. On the other hand the food retailers should strengthen the extrinsic cues of their products.

REFERENCES

1. Dunne, D., and Narasimhan, C. (1999). "The New Appeal of Private Labels". *Harvard Business Review*, 77(3).
2. Steenkamp, J. B.E.M and Dekimpe, M.G. (1997). "The Increasing Power of Store Brands: Building Loyalty and Market Share". *Long Range Planning*, 30(6), 917-930.
3. Hoch, Stephen J, (1996). "How Should National Brands Think About Private Labels?" *Sloan Management Review* 37, 89-102.
4. Putsis, William P. Jr., Dhar, Ravi (1998). "The Many Faces of Competition," *Marketing Letters* 9, 269-284.

5. Dhar, S.K. & Hoch, S. J. (1997). "Why Store Brand Penetration Varies by Retailer?", *Marketing Science*, 16 (3), 208-227.
6. Grunert, K. G., Bech-Larsen, T., Bredahl, L. 2000. Three Issues in Consumer Quality Perception and Acceptance of Dairy Products. *International Dairy Journal*, 10(8): 575-584.
7. Mowen, J. C. 1993. *Consumer Behaviour*. New York: Macmillan Publishing.
8. Tuorila, H.M., Meiselman, H.L., Cardello, A.V., Leshner, L.L. 1998. Effect of Expectations and the Definition of Products Category on the Acceptance of Unfamiliar Foods. *Food Quality and Preference* 9(6): 421-430.
9. Deliza, R., MacFie, H. J. H. 1996. The Generation of Sensory Expectation by External Cues and its Effect on Sensory Perception and Hedonic Ratings- A Review. *Journal of Sensory Studies*. 11(2): 103-128.
10. Jacoby, J., Olson, J. C., Haddock, R.A. 1971. Price, Brand Name, and Product Composition Characteristics as Determinants of Perceived Quality. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 55(6): 570-579.
11. Chernatony, L. 1991. Facilitating Consumer Choice Decisions: The Importance of Branding Cues. *British Food Journal*, 93(9): 50-56.
12. Keller, K.L. (2002). *Strategic Brand Management: Building, Measuring, and Managing Brand Equity*. Prentice-Hall India, New Delhi
13. Deliza, R., MacFie, H. J. H. 1996. The Generation of Sensory Expectation by External Cues and its Effect on Sensory Perception and Hedonic Ratings- A Review. *Journal of Sensory Studies*. 11(2): 103-128.
14. Di Monaco, R., Cavella, S., Iaccarino, T., Mincione, A., Masi, P. 2003. The Role of the Knowledge of Color and Brand Name on the Consumer's Hedonic Ratings of Tomato Purees. *Journal of Sensory Studies*, 18(5): 391-408.
15. Deliza, R., MacFie, H. J. H. 1996. The Generation of Sensory Expectation by External Cues and its Effect on Sensory Perception and Hedonic Ratings- A Review. *Journal of Sensory Studies*. 11(2): 103-128.

16. DeVecchio, D. 2001. Consumer Perceptions of Private Label Quality: The Role of Product Category Characteristics and Consumer Use of Heuristics. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 8(5): 239–249.
17. Baltas, G. 1997. Determinants of Store Brand Choice: A Behavioural Analysis. *Journal of Product and Brand Management*, 6(5): 315–324.
18. Malhotra, N. K. (2004). *Marketing Research: An Applied Orientation*, 4th ed. Delhi: Pearson Education, New Delhi.